

EFFECTS OF ASPECT RATIO ON TEST RESULTS FROM COMPRESSION-LOADED COMPOSITE COUPONS

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ABSTRACT

An experimental and analytical investigation into the effects of aspect ratio (length/width) on the strain distributions in compression-loaded composite coupons has been conducted. It is shown that transverse stress, induced by friction between the end of the coupon and the load plate, creates a region at each end of the coupon where axial and transverse strains are significantly reduced. For reliable results from a notched or impacted compression coupon, there should be no interaction between the strain redistribution around the notch or impact and the strain variation at the ends. For most common applications, an aspect ratio of at least two is recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Two common coupon tests used for characterizing composite materials are the Compression After Impact (CAI) and notched compression tests. These tests help determine the damage tolerance of a material, which often drives the design of a part. However, the results obtained from these tests are sensitive to two important factors.

The first is coupon size. For aspect ratios (length/width) of less than two, there may be interaction between strain disturbances due to an impact or centrally-located notch and strain variation at the ends where the load is introduced. This may alter the stress concentrations around the damage or notch. Also for shorter coupons, the placement of strain gages near the ends means that they that are not recording uniform strain due to the applied load, as intended. These gages have often been used as "far-field" gages to derive modulus or strain-to-failure values. A series of tests using open hole compression coupons with an aspect ratio of 1.4 resulted in unexpectedly high failure stresses [1]. Using photoelasticity, it was shown that this coupon had a lower stress concentration at the hole than a matching coupon with an aspect ratio of 2.4. Additional work by Vogler [2] investigated strain patterns in notched sandwich coupons using photoelasticity and closed-form solutions, and concluded that for the cases considered, with aspect ratios ranging from 1.6 to 3, specimen size had minimal effect on the strain field around the notch.

The second key component to reliable and consistent compression testing is shimming. Experience with hundreds of coupons of many different sizes and fixturing configurations has shown that good shimming of individual coupons to ensure uniform load introduction at the ends is difficult but very important. Strain gages are often used near the ends of coupons to ensure that the load is being introduced uniformly. Small variations in coupon machining or fixturing tolerance can lead to large differences in readings from symmetrically-placed gages. To correct this difference, small metal shims are typically inserted in the fixturing.

This paper describes an experimental and analytical investigation into the effects of aspect ratio on the strain distributions in compression-loaded composite coupons. This study developed from the testing of larger compression coupons up to 38 cm x 76 cm (15"x30") in the configuration shown in Fig. 1. During the testing of these coupons, a consistent pattern of strain variation was noticed in the gages placed near the ends for shimming purposes. It was thought that one or more of the following factors could be contributing to this effect: influence from the notch or impact damage; uneven fixturing; out-of-tolerance machining on the ends of the coupons; potting at the ends of the coupons; or friction between the end of the coupon and the load plate.

The first step in investigating the cause of the variation was to put additional gages on an unnotched coupon with an aspect ratio of 2. The same pattern of reductions in axial and transverse strain at the ends were evident, so this ruled out the possibility of influence from a notch or impact damage. A more detailed investigation was then initiated using experimental and analytical methods.

Figure 1 Test Configuration and Finite Element Model Region for Compression Coupon

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

For investigation of the extent of the end effect with experimental methods, a 38 cm x 76 cm (15" x 30") unnotched composite sandwich coupon was used. The facesheets consisted of 12 plies of AS4/8552 tape in a [45/0/-45/90/0/-45/45/0/90/-45/0/45] layup and the core was 1.90 cm (0.75") thick HRP-3/16-8.0 nomex honeycomb¹.

¹The use of these materials in this research study does not constitute endorsement of the products by *intec* or the Boeing Company.

The ends of the coupons were enclosed in a potting material. This helps to prevent delamination when machining the ends of the coupon, and also avoids brooming failures at the ends. The material used was a two-part epoxy casting system (Furane Epocast 1636A/B). For larger coupons such as this, a depth of 2.5 cm (1") is recommended.

For the photoelastic measurements, two thin strain-sensitive birefringent sheets were bonded to the tool side of the coupon in one quadrant as shown in Fig. 2. While held at a constant load, color photographs were taken of the fringe patterns. Values of the difference in principal strain magnitudes were obtained from the relationship between strain and fringe order given by the following equation [3]:

$$\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2 = Nf$$

where: ϵ_1, ϵ_2 are the principal strains
N is the fringe order
f is the fringe value of the coating.

In order to verify the results from the photoelastic coating, and to provide point values of strain for comparison with the finite element model, six biaxial resistance strain gages were applied to the other side of the compression coupon as shown in Fig. 2.

The coupon was tested in compression using a 1.1 MN (250,000 lbf) capacity servo hydraulic test frame. Fixturing and shims were used to ensure uniform loading across the width and thickness of the coupon which was verified by the four back-to-back shimming gages at the top end of the coupon and additional gages at the bottom as shown in Fig. 2. Normally edge restraints are used on a coupon of this size to prevent buckling, but for this study they were not used since the coupon was not tested to failure.

The shimming procedure for this coupon involved loading the coupon until the average strain shown by the axial gages was around 1,000 microstrain. If the high and low readings were not within 10%, metal shims ranging in thickness from 0.025 mm to 0.125 mm (0.001" to 0.005") were inserted between components of the fixturing. The coupon was then loaded again to 1,000 microstrain and the strain readings recorded. This process was repeated until all the axial gages read within 10%.

In general, small adjustments need to be made from side to side during shimming, but it is important to note that shims should be inserted in steps across the width of the coupon, instead of in one concentrated area. This will prevent gaps in the load path which could lead to nonlinearities at the beginning of the test. Shims are generally not placed directly on the ends of the coupon but between the load plates and grip heads of the test machine. With a sandwich coupon, the back-to-back readings need to be tuned carefully to make sure each facesheet is being loaded evenly. This can be a time-consuming process, but each coupon should be individually shimmed to ensure uniform load introduction, especially for coupons with small aspect ratios.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

A finite element analysis of the 38 cm x 76 cm (15"x30") compression coupon was conducted using NISA II software [4] on a PC workstation at *intec*. The goals of the model were firstly to verify and correlate strain distributions over the sandwich compression coupon with the distributions obtained from the experimental work (photoelastic and strain gages). Secondly, the model was used to investigate the influence of end conditions such as the potting and the interface between the end of the coupon and the load plate on the strain distributions. Thirdly, facesheet layup and coupon size were varied to investigate their influence on the end effect.

Three end conditions were analyzed which represent idealized situations that bounded the actual experimental conditions. For the first two conditions, no transverse slipping was permitted between the end of the coupon and the load plate (nodes along the interface were shared by elements in the coupon and the load plate). The first condition included potting, the second condition had no potting. The third condition included potting, but allowed free transverse movement (or full slip) between the coupon and the load plate. This was modeled by duplicating nodes along the interface and constraining the axial displacement. A fourth case of no potting and full slip was also run as a test case and as expected there was no strain variation at the end of the coupon.

Due to the two planes of symmetry in the setups, the finite element model covered one quarter of the setup as shown in Fig. 1. The fixtures were included in the model to represent the actual experimental conditions as closely as possible.

All elements in the models were 2nd-order two-dimensional plane stress elements with two degrees of freedom per node (NISA element ID NKPT=1). The model contained 484 elements, 1571 nodes, and 3037 unconstrained degrees of freedom. Orthotropic material properties were used for the facesheets with a stiffness ratio of 1.43 (axial modulus divided by transverse modulus) and Poisson's ratio of 0.372. The in-plane properties of the core were ignored. The applied displacement was calculated to give an average axial strain (defined by applied displacement divided by coupon length represented in the model) of 1000 microstrain in the coupon. The mesh for the model was designed so that centroids of elements corresponded to the points on the actual coupon where strain gages were located.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The photoelastic coating and the 12 strain gages on the compression coupon all gave consistent measures of the extent and magnitude of the strain variation near the end of the coupon. The photoelastic coating showed the shadow of reduced strain extended 23 cm (9") from the end of the coupon, or 30% of the entire length. The strain gages along the vertical centerline nearest the end showed a 75% reduction in transverse strain and a 15% reduction in axial strain compared to gages in the middle of the coupon. A further discussion of these results is given below.

Fig. 2 shows the values of strain represented by the fringes derived from the color of the fringe, the fringe order associated with that color, and the sensitivity of the coating. These values represent the difference between the principal strains. For the majority of the area covered by the coating, the principal strain directions coincide with the axial and transverse directions of the coupon. This must be true along the centerline of the coupon due to symmetry. Therefore a comparison can be made with the values from the strain gages, by taking the difference between the axial and the transverse gages at each of the six gage locations. These values are also shown in Fig. 2, and there is good correlation.

Fig. 3 shows the load versus strain curves for the six axial and six transverse gages on the compression coupon (see Fig. 2 for gage locations). For both axial and transverse strains, a fixture settling period can be seen in the initial loading history. At first, the axial gage nearest the end along the centerline (gage number 3) has a significantly different slope than the other axial gages, indicating lower strain increase with load. However, after 250 microstrain, the slope changes and becomes closer to the slopes of the other axial gages. The transverse gages nearest the end are very nonlinear initially, but then settle in to linear slopes that are different from the other transverse gages.

Figure 2 Location of Instrumentation on 38cm x 76cm (15"x30") Compression Coupon and Values of Photoelastic Fringes Compared with Strain Gages

Figure 3 Axial and Transverse Strain Results for a 38 cm x 76 cm (15"x30") Composite Sandwich Compression Coupon

This nonlinear behavior at low load is caused by gaps in the load path through the fixturing. These gaps are created by shims inserted in a single area between the load plate and the grip head. As load is applied, the load plate bends until the gap is filled. Until displacement is applied evenly across the width of the coupon, the center of the coupon will strain at a slower rate than at the sides. Once there is full contact between all the surfaces in the fixturing, the slope of the axial and transverse strain changes. The best way to avoid this is to shim in steps across the whole width of the coupon.

The nonlinearity at low load explains why for absolute values of axial strain, the gage on the centerline nearest the end appears to be lagging behind the gage on the side by almost 20% (at 1000 microstrain). However, the slopes of the axial strain curves after the settling-in period appear to be closer. This shows that when shimming it is important to look at slopes as well as absolute values. For comparison with the finite element model which is entirely linear, it was necessary to ignore this initial part of the load history and concentrate on the linear portion of the response. Therefore, a least squares fit value of the slope for each of the twelve gages was found between 67 MN and 134 MN (15 and 30 kips).

These values of normalized strain showed that there is only a 5% reduction in axial strain but a 55% reduction in transverse strain at the end of the coupon compared to the middle. This confirmed that there is significant transverse restraint near the ends of the coupon. Results from the analysis can be used to indicate how much reduction in the axial and transverse strains is expected and what factors influence the extent of the end effect.

All the finite element analysis cases showed different degrees of strain variation near the ends of the coupon and verified the effect observed with the experimental methods. A typical pattern of strain variation is shown in Fig. 4. Direct comparison of analytical and experimental results showed good agreement, especially for the transverse strains, as shown on Fig. 5. The closest correlation was for the end condition where all transverse movement was constrained between the loading plate and the end of the coupon. The influence of the potting on the strain distributions near the end was negligible.

The implications of these results are that on any size coupon, there will be a region near the ends where axial and transverse strains are reduced because of friction with the loading plates. This indicates that gages placed close to the ends will be influenced by the end conditions, and therefore should not be used for deriving strain-to-failure or modulus values. If gages near the end are used for shimming, it should be recognized that a gage along the centerline will read a lower axial strain than gages towards the edges. The amount of this difference will depend on the aspect ratio of the coupon and the orthotropic properties of the material.

In order to examine the influence of aspect ratio on the extent of this end effect, three additional coupon sizes were analyzed. Each coupon was 20.3 cm (8") long, and the width was varied to give aspect ratios of 1, 2, and 4. Quarter symmetry was applied for the models and the same orthotropic material properties were used. Displacements of 0.1 cm (0.04") were applied directly to the ends of the coupons (with no fixturing) to produce an average axial strain of 1000 microstrain. The ends were restrained to prevent transverse movement.

The results are presented in Fig. 5, which shows the distribution of axial and transverse strains along the length of each of the three coupons with different aspect ratios. It can be seen that for an aspect ratio of four, the axial strain in the majority of the coupon is just over 1000 microstrain (1009 at the middle of the coupon) and is above 950 microstrain except for 6% of the coupon length at the loaded end. However, for an aspect ratio of 2, the axial strain in the middle is 1036 microstrain and is below 950 microstrain for 9% of the length from the end. For an aspect ratio of 1, the axial strain in the middle is 1084 microstrain and is below 950 microstrain for 14% of the length from the end. The effect of the aspect ratio on transverse strain follows the same trend.

These results indicate that coupons with smaller aspect ratios have proportionally larger regions of strain variation at each end. Also, the axial strain in the middle becomes greater to make up for the reduction in strain at each end. In order to have a large region of uniform strain in an unnotched coupon, an aspect ratio of at least two is recommended. For the properties used in this study, this limits the variation of axial strain to within 5% of the average coupon strain for 80% of the length of the coupon.

Figure 4 Axial Strain Distribution from Quarter-Symmetry Finite Element Model of 38 cm x 76 cm (15"x30") Composite Compression Coupon

Figure 5 Strain Distributions Along the Length of Compression Coupons from Finite Element Models

For a notched or impact damaged coupon, the same recommendation applies. However, the importance of a large aspect ratio is even greater to avoid interactions between strain disturbances from a notch or impact damage and strain variations from the end effect. Also, these analytical models assume that the coupon is loaded evenly. For a shorter coupon, the influence of nonuniform loading will be greater than on a longer coupon of the same width, and good shimming procedures become more critical. For strain gage placement, finding a true far-field region in a notched or damaged coupon that is not affected by disturbances from either the ends or the center may require analysis of the particular configuration being tested. However, a good rule-of-thumb is to avoid the vertical centerline of the coupon (except for shimming gages), and place the gages at least 10% of the length of the coupon away from the ends and the edges.

CONCLUSIONS / SUMMARY

An investigation of strain variation at the ends of compression-loaded sandwich coupons has been conducted using experimental and analytical techniques. The conclusions from this study are:

- A region of reduced axial and transverse strain exists at the ends of compression coupons. The extent of strain variation near the ends of the coupons depends on the aspect ratio of the coupon. The region of reduced strain is proportionally larger for smaller aspect ratios.
- The variation is primarily caused by the restraint of the coupon in the transverse direction. This restraint is caused by friction between the end of the composite coupon and the steel load plates resulting in a transverse compressive stress near the coupon end.
- A minimum aspect ratio of 2 is recommended for unnotched compression coupons to ensure an adequate region of uniform strain in the middle of the coupon.
- For coupons with notches or impact damage, a minimum aspect ratio of 2 is also recommended to avoid interactions between strain disturbances from the notch or impact damage and strain variations from the end effect.
- Strain gages placed near the ends of the coupon for shimming should not be used for deriving modulus or strain-to-failure values unless the influence from the transverse restraint at the ends is accounted for and very careful shimming is performed.
- Shimming of individual coupons is recommended to ensure even load introduction at the ends of the coupon. Shims should be applied in steps to prevent gaps which could lead to nonlinear behavior at the beginning of the test. If gages along the centerline are used for shimming, it should be recognized that lower strain readings will be expected than from gages nearer the sides because of the end effect. The importance of careful shimming is greater for coupons with smaller aspect ratios.

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